

THE CONCEPT OF THE INFORMED SOCIETY AND ITS SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL DESCRIPTION

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Abstract: The article talks about the historical evolution of the concept of information, information society, its origins, and its essence. Also, this article analyzes the historical facts, socio-philosophical reasons and current processes related to the origin of the concept of information society.

Key words: information, information society, integration, globalization, internet, computer, electronics, cybernetics, social, philosophical.

INTRODUCTION

The 21st century is the era of globalization, the age of technology. Globally, the development and advancement of technologies and communications is causing unique economic, social, and cultural situations. In the era of globalization, societies are rapidly integrating. This integration has greatly accelerated the ability of people in the society to conduct global social relations in a common and common way. Mutual social relations in the new era gradually led to the wide spread of complex morality, mass culture, which calls for the same morals and cultural rules for everyone, and is now being called "21st century democracy". One of the negative aspects of this is that national, regional and historically formed boundaries of moral and cultural norms, specific to one society, have been replaced by global morality, which consists of a mixture of moral, cultural and sociological influences of different societies. culture is taking over. Codes of ethics and moral boundaries are more important than ever. Today, duty, responsibility, conscience, moral norms are urgent issues in all societies, especially for us.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Although the term "information society" began to be used when computerization became widespread and information and digital technologies began to actively develop, the concept of "information society" appeared in the 1940s with the emergence of cybernetics. This concept is associated with the names of American scientists K. Shannon, N. Wiener, D. von Neumann, English thinker and cryptographer A. Turing, Russian mathematician A. N. Kolmogorov. The Japanese version of the term "Information Society" appeared in a 1961 conversation between Kisho Kurokawa and Tadao Umesao. Later, this term was used in the works of T. Umesao and F. Machlup, which appeared almost simultaneously - in Japan and the USA.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. "Today the world is going through profound changes. Economic mutual globalization and increasing interdependence, strong and ubiquitous population migration. Changes in the social structure are deepening and societies are developing rapidly. When such situations occur, complex changes can lead to inter-ethnic conflicts, and conflicts are still developing in different parts of the world. The existence of society - national, ethnic, inter-ethnic relations, problems, tasks, their solutions, were not

solved by the old tools and methods used in the past. "Life has put new problems on the agenda - approach to the national issue and resolute rejection of the old ways."

Today's period is the period when societies are actively integrating with each other, the development of information technology, communication, and technologies is becoming globalized. In the period when the establishment of the information society is accelerating, it is increasingly becoming a vital necessity for us to study it in every way, and to study the history and causes of the origin of such a society is one of the main issues on the agenda, because today we are gradually moving towards this society.

From the most primitive period of development to the present advanced period, information has become important in determining the regulatory function of mankind. Information forms the basis of human gnesiological-rational and irrational knowledge. Information has long been essential to the survival of Christians as a species and their subsequent revolution. The initial form of information developed intuitively, i.e. in the form of a desire to save oneself, and later the information collected by people gathered together and took the form of speech. An important feature of the human mind is that it has the ability to store, process, and transmit information, and based on the given information, the mind has the ability to process and change information itself. The emergence of communication in people created the oral form of information. People's desire to understand the universe more deeply led to the creation of pictures and figures, which formed hieroglyphs representing certain meanings, i.e. "information of thought" and led to the creation of hieroglyphs, the development was mainly due to the accumulation of information. The discovery of writing gave rise to the written form of information along with the communication form. By accelerating the development of functions of information [storage, collection, transmission], writing has raised the communication between people to a new level, and this has given an important impetus to the development of science, aesthetic, ethical, rational knowledge and the development of societies. The difference between writing and speech information is that it is not limited in terms of space [distance] and time [time]. Written information brought a new direction and improvement to the functions and tasks of information until now, and also made the functions of state management more complicated and expanded.

The term "information society" has been used since the 60-70s of the last century in Japan and America. Basically, "Information society" refers to societies with advanced information technologies, communications, and information infrastructures that have a high possibility of receiving, storing, collecting, and transmitting information. " is used. There is no clear gnesiological, empirical and philosophical alternative definition of this concept. There are different views on its origin, for example, the origin of the "Information Society" corresponds to the period of the industrial revolution, during which production was automated, with the possibility of long-distance transportation, modernized

The systems believe that monitoring trends are related to communication and remote control. Steinfeld and Salvaggio divide the information society into 5 directions: Economic (production), consumption, technological, critical and multidimensional.

According to the philosopher R.F. Abdeev, there were two types of debates in the explanation of the information phenomenon. Attributive and functional concepts of information are opposite to each other. "Attributists" qualify information as a characteristic of all material objects, an attribute of matter. "Functionalists", on the contrary, associate

information with the activity of self-organizing systems, believing that it appeared only with the emergence of life.

According to a team of scholars such as Daphne R. Raban, Avishag Gordon, and Dorit Geifman: A review of the evolution of the term "Information Society" shows that we believe that the region has reached the point where a core and a periphery can be defined. Definitions to explain the concept of information society have taken different forms during the last 30 years.

The concept of the information society is one of the most relevant phenomena of our century, and many experts have given their descriptions to this concept in their works.

The concept of information society refers to a country or region where information and communication technologies are fully used and are part of everyday life as a factor of socio-economic development.

An information society is a society in which the creation, dissemination, use, integration and manipulation of information is an important economic, political and cultural activity.

An information society is a society in which information is a necessary condition for the main product or other products. In fact, in the information society, the performance of workers and the success of organizations depends on their ability to use information.

Information society is a set of social relations based on information and communication technologies. The focus of this society is on information as an element influencing knowledge.

The information society is a post-industrial society whose main drivers are digital information and communication technologies.

Information society - a society characterized by a high level of information intensity in everyday life and workplaces of most citizens; this society will be able to use common or compatible technologies for a wide range of personal, social, educational and business activities and to transfer, receive and exchange digital information rapidly between locations regardless of distance.

Many philosophers-scientists and historians have divided the dynamics of human development (civilization) into three stages: agrarian civilization, post-industrial civilization and industrial civilization. Today's information society is considered as the fourth wave or the fourth civilization.

CONCLUSION. As we mentioned above, the information society brings innovative development to many areas, especially to the social and cultural life of people. In particular, in our country, including people in higher educational institutions, digitalization of the education system, organization of innovative educational institutions, raising the freedom and legal awareness of citizens, freedom, openness, and transparency, ensuring the full participation of citizens in public administration. the role of technology is incomparable.

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